

IR1318-16 was selected from Jin Heung/IR262-43-8-11//Calady and IR262 from Peta/Peta*2//TN1. Its short stature and yield capacity originated from TN1 and the large, translucent kernels from Calady. Jin Heung may be responsible for Calpearl's short grains and Earlirose provided earliness. Calrose 76 has cold tolerance, lodging resistance, and high grain fertility.

Calpearl yields 10 t/ha, about 10% more than the average japonica grown in California and performs well when planted late. Its grains ripen 5 or more days earlier than most japonicas (see table). It can be harvested before the October rainy season, and has 5% lower grain moisture at harvest, which saves fuel during grain drying. Calpearl is easily combine harvested.

Its only disadvantage is that its large translucent kernels closely resemble

Average yield and agronomic characteristics of California rices.

Variety ^a	Tests (no.)	Year	Yield (t/ha)	Moisture at harvest (%)	Days to 50% heading	Plant height (cm)	Percent lodging	Seedling vigor ^b	Hull type ^c
S-201 j	20	1980-84	8.9	19.7	95	89	33	4.2	S
M9 j	20	1980-84	8.4	21.6	93	94	57	4.1	S
M-201 j	20	1980-84	9.4	21.4	94	86	9	4.1	S
Calmochi-202 jg	20	1980-84	8.3	22.2	99	94	28	4.0	S
M-302 j	17	1980-84	9.0	19.9	103	94	24	4.2	S
M-401 j	17	1980-84	9.1	20.0	106	94	52	4.3	S
M7 j	17	1980-84	8.9	21.0	110	97	15	4.4	S
Calrose 76 j	12	1980-84	9.1	18.4	110	97	22	4.3	P
Calpearl j	10	1982-84	9.9	16.3	89	84	20	4.7	P
M-101 j	10	1982-84	8.7	18.7	88	86	43	4.6	S
California Belle i	9	1982-84	7.6	16.9	88	102	42	3.5	S
L-202 i	9	1982-84	9.1	18.5	95	81	3	3.6	S

^aj = japonica, g = glutinous, i = indica. ^b Subjective score: 1 = very poor, 5 = excellent. CS = smooth, P = pubescent.

those of California medium-grain rices. California's Grain Inspection Service has classified Calpearl as a medium-grained variety, but milled Calpearl rice meets

US Department of Agriculture short-grain standards. Calpearl was planted on 24% (32,376 ha) of California riceland in 1983. *ℒ*

ACK-5 for direct seeded rainfed conditions

B. S. Shah, S. K. Lad, and D. B. Gavit, Mahatma Phule Agricultural University, Kolhapur 416004, Maharashtra, India

ACK-5 was developed from D.6-2-2/IR8 at the College of Agriculture in Kolhapur, India, and released for general cultivation in May 1985.

Performance of ACK-5 in station and adaptive trials, Kolhapur, India.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)		
	1983	1984	Average
<i>Station trial</i>			
Direct seeded ^a			
ACK-5	4.7	4.9	4.8
RDN185-2	5.7	4.5	5.1
Transplanted ^b			
ACK-5	5.7	3.3	4.5
RDN185-2	4.1	3.0	3.9
<i>Adaptive trial^c</i>			
Direct seeded			
ACK-5	3.8 (10)	4.0 (14)	3.9
RDN185-2	3.4 (10)	3.4 (14)	3.4
Transplanted			
ACK-5	3.3 (3)	3.0 (23)	3.2
RDN185-2	3.4 (3)	3.0 (23)	3.2

^a Mean of 2 locations. ^b Mean of 3 replications. ^c Numbers in parentheses indicate number of locations.

The semidwarf can be grown direct seeded in rainfed conditions, or transplanted. It matures in 120-125 d when direct seeded and in 110-115 d when transplanted. Grains are short and bold (length: breadth 2.25) without white belly. Cooking quality and taste are acceptable and it has 8.8% crude protein. Recovery is 65% with hulling, 60% with milling, and 54% head rice. Flaked rice is better than that of local varieties.

ACK-5 was evaluated for 8 yr under upland conditions. It yielded

significantly higher than several local varieties. Performance in direct seeded and transplanted station and adaptive trials is compared with that of popular, short-duration RDN185-2 (HS-17/TN1) in the table. ACK-5 yield potential is 4 to 6 t/ha. It yielded 4.9 t/ha in direct-seeded trials in 1984, and 5.7 t/ha in transplanted trials in 1983.

ACK-5 is moderately susceptible to blast but is tolerant of Fe chlorosis and drought stress. It has 20 d seed dormancy. *ℒ*

Katrin: a new rice variety for Tanzania

H.M. Ching'ang'a, Tanzania Agricultural Research Institute, Private Bag, Ifakara, Tanzania

IET2397, a strain developed in India, was released as Katrin for general cultivation in Tanzania. A derivative of HR19/2x IR8, Katrin is semidwarf (90 cm), resistant to blast and lodging, photoperiod sensitive, and has medium duration (135 d). Average yield is 5.6 t/ha. Grains are long, slender, and

translucent white with good cooking quality. Amylose content is 30%. Grain length-breadth ratio is 3.43, and volume expansion is 4.2. Fifty percent flowering is achieved in 102 d. It produces about 10 panicles/hill and 1,000-grain wt is 30 g. *ℒ*

CR666, the 60-day rice strains

C. Gangadharan, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, India

CR666 (Sattari/Rasi/Kalinga III) lines

are some of the earliest rice strains. Because of their extreme earliness, they make a harvest possible in unirrigated drought-prone tracts of India and elsewhere.

Many CR666 lines that mature in 60 d have been identified. Some are intermediate in stature and grain size, and yield higher than the parents Sattari and Kalinga III although 10-20 d earlier than either. In progeny row trials during 1984 kharif, the strains were direct seeded and fertilized 1 wk after germination with 40 kg N/ha. Data on some of the promising lines are given in the table.

Subsequent bulk trials in 1985

Some agronomic characters of elite CR666 selections and their parents. Cuttack, India.

Culture or variety	Height (cm)	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Grain size
CR666-36-69	85	60	3.3	Long bold
CR666-36-134	85	60	3.7	Long slender
CR666-36-162	80	57	2.9	Medium slender
CR666-36-173	85	60	4.0	Medium slender
CR666-36-322	90	58	3.8	Long slender
Sattari	70	70	2.3	Short bold
Kalinga III	125	80	3.8	Long slender
Rasi	85	115	4.2	Short bold

confirmed that the lines had a yield potential of 1.8 to 2.5 t/ha, comparable to the early parent Sattari. There has been an upgrading in height and grain

quality over Sattari, while reducing duration by more than 10 d. The productivity of these lines is more than 30 kg/ha daily. *ℓ*

DR92, a rice variety for low and medium altitudes

K.R. Dhiman and R.N. Rai, Indian Council for Agricultural Research, NEH Region, Sikkim Centre, Tadong, Gangtok 737102, India

DR92, a variety suitable for cultivation in puddled and upland conditions, has been released by Sikkim State Varietal Release Committee. A selection from the IET series, DR92 is medium tall, tillers profusely, and has good panicle exertion. Panicles are compact and

DR92 performance in Sikkim, India.

Variety	Plant ht (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Filled spikelets/panicle (no.)	Maturity (d)	Yield (t/ha)
DR92	90	14	146	130	5.5
Chirakey	119	9	94	145	1.7
Addey	115	8	89	148	2.0
Kanchi Addey	125	10	90	150	1.4

number of filled spikelets per panicle is high. The grains are medium sized and bold; kernels are light red and glutinous. DR92 is resistant to blast and stem

borer. It yields 40-60% more than predominant local varieties Chirakey, Addey, and Kanchi Addey (see table). *ℓ*

Three new high yielding rice varieties

J.K. Roy and K.Prasad, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRRI), Cuttack 6, Orissa, India

The Orissa State Seed Sub-committee in May 1985 released three promising CRRRI-developed varieties for general cultivation in Orissa. CR404-56-1 (Neela), CR407-19 (Sarasa), and CR190-103 (Udaya) have built-in resistance to major insect pests such as gall midge (GM), brown planthopper (BPH), and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH).

Neela is a selection from CR94-1512-6/ Pusa 2-21. It has semidwarf stature (65-70 cm), 90-d maturity (seed to seed), medium bold grains, and yields 3.0-3.5

t/ha. A derivative of PTB21 and PTB18 parents (CR94 series), Neela is resistant to GM, green leafhopper (GLH), and BPH. It is suitable for direct seeding in uplands in kharif and for transplanting in rabi where GM is a problem in the early crop.

Sarasa, a selection from CR94-1512-6/ Ratna, has semidwarf stature (80-85 cm), is weakly photoperiod sensitive, matures in 120-125 d in kharif (1 wk earlier in rabi at Cuttack), has long slender grains with head rice recovery of 50%, and yields 4-6 t/ha. A derivative of CR94, it is resistant to GM, BPH, and WBPH. Sarasa can withstand submergence for 7-10 d in the early vegetative stage. Sarasa is recommended for areas that are affected by early flooding followed by late season drought such as those in the Orissa coastal belt.

Udaya, a selection from CR129-118/CR57-49-2, is semidwarf (95-100 cm) and medium maturing (130 d). It has long bold grains and yields 5-6 t/ha. It is resistant to **BPH**, **WBPH**, **GM**, and **GLH**, and is tolerant of blast and tungro. Udaya is suitable for medium lands in kharif and rabi, particularly for areas where **BPH** is endemic. It has become popular in the second crop season in Cuttack and Puri Districts, where **BPH** infestation had caused farmers to switch to other crops. *ℓ*

Individuals, organizations, and media are invited to quote or reprint articles or excerpts from articles in the IRRN.